

SEMIOTIC MEANS IN ADVERTISING LANGUAGE: AS AN EXAMPLE OF MODERN BRANDS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the semiotic tools used in advertising texts, banners, and visual images of modern brands operating in Uzbekistan. In the article, based on a linguosemiotic approach, it is studied how brands communicate with their audience through symbols (logos, colors, metaphors, images). The study analyzes the connotative and denotative layers of advertising language, their interpretation in a cultural context. The results of the analysis show that advertising language has been formed not only as an informative, but also as a communicative tool carrying a cultural, moral, and aesthetic load.*

Keywords: *advertising language, semiotics, brand, symbol, image, connotation, denotation, linguosemiotics, cultural code, marketing discourse*

Introduction: Modern advertising is not just a text conveying information about a product, but a social phenomenon with deep cultural, psychological, and visual semantic loads. The signs, symbols, and images used in the language of advertising serve to convey to the audience not the product or service, but the value, feeling, and experience associated with it. In particular, the advertising market in Uzbekistan is developing in harmony with national mentality, values, and aesthetic views. This necessitates the study of the semiotic expression of national culture through advertising language and brand symbols (logo, color, image).

Literature analysis and methods. The research was conducted on the basis of semiotic theory. Main theoretical sources: F. de Saussure (sign system), Ch. S. Peirce (tricotomy model), Yu. Lotman (semiosphere), and Roland Bart (advertising and fashion semiotics). The works of Leiss, Kline, and Jhalley (1997) and Williamson

(1978) on advertising semiotics were also used.

As a method:

- Visual-semiotic analysis - semantics of colors, shapes, images;
- Discursive analysis - language units in advertising texts;
- Linguocultural approach - revealing the connection with national code and values;
- Brand analysis - using the example of advertisements of such brands in Uzbekistan as "Artel," "Makro," "Sello," "Neftchi," "Samarkand Darvoza."

Results and discussion: According to the results of the analysis, the following semiotic features were identified in the advertising texts of Uzbek brands:

- Colors: "green" - confidence and health (Artel), "blue" - coolness and confidence (Cello).
- Images: family, national cuisine, mother, child - signs promoting a reliable and warm atmosphere.
- Logos: often minimalistic, but associated with national ornaments or letter shapes (Makro, Samarkand Darvoza).
- Phraseological units: "Quality is paramount for us!," "Convenience is for you!," "Honesty begins with us" reflect brand values.

Semiotic units used in advertising texts sell not only the product, but also values: trust, quality, nationality, honesty. This gives grounds to consider the language of advertising not as a simplified commercial language, but as a cultural and spiritual discourse.

Conclusion. Modern brands operating in Uzbekistan successfully use semiotic means in their advertising strategies. The system of signs visible in advertising texts and images is the intersection point of national thinking and global marketing. The image of a brand, formed through the language of advertising, is a connotative combination of visual and linguistic signs, which has a direct impact on the consciousness, values, and culture of the people.

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